

ANALYSIS OF STRESS VULNERABILITY OF PHYSICAL EDUCATION STUDENTS OF NORTHERN INDIA UNIVERSITIES

Meenu

Research Scholar, Department of Physical Education, Chaudhary Devi Lal University, Sirsa, Haryana

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Abstract:

The purpose of the study was to analyze the stress vulnerability of physical education students of northern India universities. Total of 150 physical education students of different university of northern India i.e. M.D.U Rohtak, Panjab University Chandigarh, Punjabi University Patiala, K.U.K University and Chaudhary devil al university Sirsa was selected for the present study by using an interview schedule containing closed-ended questions. Their ages is ranging between 18 to 29 years. To measure the Stress Vulnerability Scale which contains 20 items devised by L.H. Miller and A.D. Smith was applied. To examine the hypothesis of the study descriptive statistics like mean and standard deviation were used. To determine the significant difference among all the students One Way Analysis of Variance and F-test will be used in the selected parameters (Verma, 2013). The level of significance set at 0.05 level.

Key Words: Burnout, Stress, Badminton, Male & Physical Education

Introduction:

Sports can have both negative and positive impacts on athlete development. Several sports can develop athletes self confidence, physical well being, health, ability to work and encouragement to excel with others. The downside of extensive involvement in sports by athletes involves developing expectation by coaches and the public to be successful at any cost. Another major cause of stress is the time management (Hanton et al, 2005).

Objective of the Study: To measure stress vulnerability of physical education students of northern India universities.

Method and Procedure:

Total of 150 physical education students of different university of northern India i.e. M.D.U Rohtak, Panjab University Chandigarh, Punjabi University Patiala, K.U.K University and Chaudhary devil al university Sirsa was selected for the present study. Their ages is ranging between 18 to 29 years. To measure the Stress Vulnerability Scale which contains 20 items devised by L.H. Miller and A.D. Smith was applied. To examine the hypothesis of the study descriptive statistics like mean and standard deviation were used. To determine the significant difference among all the students One Way Analysis of Variance and F-test will be used in the selected parameters (Verma, 2013). The level of significance set at 0.05 level.

Results:

Graph 1: Mean Difference of the stress vulnerability of physical education students of northern India universities

Table 1: Descriptive statistics of the stress vulnerability of Physical education students of northern India universities

Universities	N	Mean	S.D
M.D.U, Rhk	50	34.32	10.99
Punjab University, Chandigarh	50	31.74	10.42
Punjabi University, Patiala	50	31.35	8.75

The above table-1 indicates that all the universities of northern India universities consisting of equal samples with fifty in each group. On the stress vulnerability mean value 34.32 for M.D.U Rhk, 31.74 for P.U Chandigarh and 31.35 for Punjabi university respectively.

Conclusions:

Physical education students of M.D.U Rohtak University showed higher level of stress vulnerability as compared to P.U Chandigarh and Panjabi University, Patiala (Table No1).

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